

SWOC ANALYSIS OF ZOMATO – A CASE OF ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

The advent of digital technologies has increased the use of creativity and has reshaped the existing markets. The worldwide boom in the digital industry has influenced the Indian economy. With digitalization, the food industry has adopted an e-commerce platform for the customers to place an order through mobile-based apps and get delivery of food at their doorsteps. Among many such service providers, Zomato is the most popular apps providing an online food delivery service to explore restaurants to the customers. This study analyses the marketing mix, positioning strategies, competitive and SWOC analysis of Zomato. The overall analysis suggested Zomato explore rural areas and provide virtual restaurant tours to enhance service capabilities. The study concludes that Zomato's positioning strategy is well defined to capture the market but requires to frame more strategies to survive in a competitive environment. Implications of Zomato have been discussed.

Keywords: Online food delivery, Marketing mix strategies, SWOC analysis, Competitive analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalization has facilitated the use of the Internet not only between different business firms but also between businesses and customers. Customers not only access the Internet to order the product online, but also to compare costs, features of the product, and after-sale service facilities they would obtain if they buy the product from a specific store [1]. The Internet is becoming an increasingly common platform to facilitate searching, choosing, and buying content. Online food ordering aggregators (OFA's) offer a range of options and conveniences that enable consumers with a simple tap on their smartphones to order from restaurants. As many new online delivery channels compete to create their positions in markets and create customers in many metropolitan cities in India, the business of delivering restaurant meals to the home is evolving rapidly [2]. Since the past five years, food delivery services have become very successful enterprises, even though these businesses can quickly receive their orders from online channels and service several restaurants in any given local market. Besides, the demand for delivery services between restaurants has increased significantly, considering how busy people are these days. Many individuals will place orders at a restaurant in their free time and then go to pick up their food. However, with the extremely busy lives of individuals, they now want to be able to have access to a delivery service that can very quickly carry them food. As such, the popularity of food delivery services has exploded as it relates to the launch of these new companies combined with online applications that allow them to very quickly take orders.

II. OBJECTIVES

The study has the following objectives:

- (1) To identify the various principles of the marketing mix.
- (2) To analyze the marketing mix followed by Zomato.
- (3) To explore marketing enhancement techniques.
- (4) To analyze the Zomato food delivery system using the SWOC framework.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Analysis of this study is composed of secondary information. Therefore, for data collection, written sources are taken into consideration. The study analyses Zomato's marketing techniques and also suggests approaches to promote sustainable growth. The secondary data is extracted from the Zomato website, journal articles, journals, and business websites.

IV. COMPANIES AND FIRMS

One of the most rapid advances in the e-commerce sector has been online food delivery. This industry has changed the way people think about food because customers can now choose from a wide range of cuisines from a variety of restaurants listed online, globally and at any time. Below is the mentioned list of online food companies with their country of origin and year of establishment.

Table-1: Exhibits the list of online food delivery companies

Sl. No	List of Companies	Country of origin	Year of establishment
1	Domino's Pizza	Ypsilanti, Michigan, U.S.	1961
2	Just Eat	London, England, UK	2001
3	Grubhub	Chicago, Illinois, U.S.	2004
4	Zomato	Haryana, India	2008
5	Postmates	San Francisco, California, US	2011
6	FoodPanda	Berlin, Germany	2012
7	Deliveroo	London, England, UK	2013
8	DoorDash	San Francisco, California, US	2013
9	Swiggy	Bangalore, India	2014
10	UberEats	San Francisco, California, U.S.	2014

V. OVERVIEW OF ZOMATO

In 2008, Zomato commenced with the name 'Foodiebay,' and in 2010 it was renamed as Zomato' [3]. It started its operations in Delhi 12 years ago with a home project and became one of the biggest food aggregators globally. Currently operates in 24 countries, 10000+ cities worldwide, enabling more people to see better food and aims not only to link people with food in any sense but also to work closely with restaurants to create a sustainable ecosystem.

Zomato's Principles Scheme:[4]

(1) Resilience

Zomato, when faced with difficult times, drives itself beyond its skill. They approach it only with versatility as they expect ambiguity.

(2) Acceptance

Feedbacks taken from customers are split into constructive data and the company continues to improve its functions even more efficiently.

(3) Ownership

They treat every issue as their own and push the change.

(4) Humbleness

It's always about 'us' above 'me'. During individual achievements, they do not lose themselves in pride or trust but concentrate in every way on being our simple selves.

(5) Spark

They believe in faith, advocate for it, and are evangelists.

(6) Judgment

In the majority of cases, they try to get it right judgment.

VI. MARKETING STRATEGIES

Zomato was supposed to be the site of the Foodies' hangout. Currently, it was renamed as Food Network. The food market in India in 2015 was around 23 trillion Indian rupees, according to the Boston Consulting company, and by 2020 it is projected to cross 42 lakh crores and is revolutionizing the experience of foodservice delivery, technology plays its main role [5].

1. Segmenting:

Zomato targets the 18-35 age group who are involved in dining out and want to have sufficient restaurant information. A larger target segment was found by Zomato Professionals who like to dine out in the office and even they like to munch food if it is delivered at their places of the stay [6]. They organize some entertainment and food festivals called Zealand in many cities in the experiential events category. Zomato claims to provide a satisfying experience to the customers towards food. It strategizes to do so by introducing new food-centred products for banqueting out and delivery segments.

2. Target

Zomato aims to capture young people between the ages of 18-35; individuals who often want to dine-out with their loved ones. It aims to get clients who regularly give ratings and feedbacks about the location to get more customers in the belief the place is worthwhile good and value for money. People who like more food and those who wish to share it with other individuals are also aimed to capture. These individuals just want to know where the best foods in town are available and frequent those restaurants. All online opinion seekers from restaurants are the target of consumption [7].

3. Positioning

The website is popular among young people because they want to explore many places to dine outside and relish the food with family and friends [8].

VII. ZOMATO'S MARKETING MIX

1. Product:

Zomato is an app/website that displays its users the restaurants and menu of the available food and allows the customer to place an order online. Zomato offers the user with information of the restaurant, its photos, charges, menus, and even reviews of the customer and has given a platform where customers can express their opinions with respect to the food and service of the food providers [9]. In its marketing, the core services include systems for Point of Sale, Restaurant Expedition and Delivery Management, and Table bookings in advance.

2. Price:

For restaurants, Zomato does not charge for placing their information on their website portal. Zomato earns its returns is the restaurant advertising which they display on their website. They promote the restaurant's banner that gives them full exposure to the user who logs their website. They also offer consulting services to restaurants as to when they will open their next outlet for the restaurant chains. It has increased its Gold membership rates and also began cross-selling during checkouts and introduced a phased delivery fee as well. Lunch is the most common meal to be ordered online and the most preferred payment form is card payment. Unsurprisingly, it is found, 95% of respondents ordered online food because of promotional deals and discounts, and 84% due to hassle-free and time-saving [10].

3. Place:

The use of a mobile smartphone app for customers is to help them see and give orders which helped the restaurants to deliver consumers' orders instantly and this has led to the growth in the use of mobile phones and computers and provided good business to the service industry [11]. Zomato, an online service is available on Windows platform, Android, and iOS platforms. It is available in 24 countries which include India, Australia, the USA, Chile, Malaysia, United Arab Emirates, Portugal, South Africa, and many more. The UI is user-friendly and has nine language options viz. English, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Turkish, Slovak, Indonesian, Polish, and Italian [12]. Also, they are active on various social platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, and Instagram which are used to engage with customers. Moreover, in comparison to mail-order days of the Indian Postal Service, the logistic system has a considerable change. The distribution and delivery channels can now be regarded as capable of meeting consumer standards of speed and timeliness of delivery with the mushrooming of many private logistic services [13].

4. Promotion:

Advertising for Zomato is very precise, making it highly targeted. They have an in-built platform for analytics that runs a lot of queries and gets Useful knowledge out there. This renders it extremely targeted. Zomato is Renowned for its incredible offers than its rivals. Advertises Zomato Get great deals with animation and cartoons with a caption Faster delivery. In marketing, Zomato is aggressive when It uses guerrilla marketing in contrast to others [14]. Zomato organized the Zomaland festival as a part of a promotion, a food festival with entertainment like music, dance, and gagsters [15]. Zomato gives concessions and promo codes to attract consumers.

5. Physical Evidence:

Zomato is a service that does not offer any of its products and it has no specific physical presence. The delivery system consists of employees who deliver the food placed through an order from the website or application of Zomato. The company acts as a third-party scheme.

6. People:

Zomato consists of a strong team of about 5,000 people who strive to provide the best services to the customers. Small companies that outsource their non-core business operations, such as the delivery of food, are growing; historically this practice was followed only by large businesses. The result was the rising attention and exploration of an increasing number of proprietors and managers of the importance of outsourcing food delivery services [16].

7. Process:

Customer needs to login in with their registered phone number and email address under Zomato. The location of the customer gets traced and a list of restaurants of that area is displayed with the menu which can be browsed and the order can be placed. Payment towards the order can be made by cash mode or through online modes to wither. The restaurant will approve the order as soon as it is made and dispatches it. Zomato demands input after the delivery of food. Therefore, the whole process is made simple for the user to have a hassle-free experience. To dine at the restaurant, paper waste can be avoided because they operate on a tablet so the process does not require paperwork. For example, they do not use records to take the order. Also, it has a

digitized menu card. There is no need to wait for the waiters to take the order from a customer heading to the restaurant. They get the order as soon as one occupies a seat and It will be confirmed to the customer as soon as the order is ready. So, despite the food being ready, there would not be any problem with late delivery [17].

VIII. DIFFERENTIATION MARKETING STRATEGY OF ZOMATO

1 Strategy:

Zomato designs creative systems which engross a customer's interest. The Zomato Gold is a premium membership reward system that offers BOGO (Buy One, Get One) and two plus two free beverages to customers as a part of a unique dine-out experience. Presently, 600,000 customers have Zomato Gold. This program has helped consumers to eat out more which has led to an increase in customer rush at a higher rate.

2.Strong Brand Name:

A strong brand name is a must for keeping its brand into existence in the market and Zomato successfully has been able to build its brand that resounds with confidence and easy accessibility. Many competing brands such as Food Panda and Uber eats have been in this business, but in comparison to Zomato, they need to put more effort into creating their brand awareness. It has been able to continuously modernize through multiple channels and has ensured that the advantages it has generated are built on.

3. Focus on technology:

Zomato's greatest benefit offered to its clients is its attractively designed user interface. The app is very much appealing and user-friendly which has succeeded to provide a competitive edge over other brands.

Even for a beginner, the swiftness at which the website of Zomato opens and mobile application is very fast and simple to access. In developing a persuasive UI for its customers, Zomato offers a lot of attention and effort. It has data analytics which has added to its success in an amazing manner.

Since it is highly data-driven, Zomato was able to gain a competitive advantage. The company can get operational benefits and commercial productivities such as estimation of delivery time, optimization of logistics, advertisement, and arrangement of supply.

The goal of Zomato is to introduce the cloud kitchen model, to extend its business with limited resources and less fixed costs. Such importance on the development of technology at Zomato will allow it to lead in the market.

With most businesses doing exceptionally well in the market, the food industry is facing a lot of competition from many entrants. Google Maps are used which provides a directory of local restaurants, including customer feedback, pictures, and ratings on the site. The key advantage over Google Maps is that the menu listing for Maps has not begun. Zomato is also a favourite restaurant discovery platform for clients.

IX. SWOC ANALYSIS OF ZOMATO

SWOC Analysis is the most widely used technique for monitoring and assessing a company's overall competitive role and its climate. Its primary objective is to evaluate strategies for developing a company business plan that synchronizes the organization's capital and skills with the needs of the world in which it operates [18]. Businesses use SWOC framework to analyze Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges of their businesses, competition and products. SWOC is a thorough analysis of the environment in which the industry runs and aids in the projection of different facets of the environment as well as incorporating them into the organization's decision-making mechanism [19].

Strengths

Zomato has the following Strengths:

- (1) Customers review Zomato as a 'Specialty Product' which only offers foods & restaurants.
- (2) Brand awareness is very high among the customers and is rated as the top product of the mind of customers.
- (3) Global presence in 25 countries with more than 1.5 million restaurants as their members.
- (4) Advanced and updated technology with powerful and dedicated employees of more than 1200 working under its roof.
- (5) It offers a modest & user-friendly interface.
- (6) It adopts an encroaching and pioneering marketing strategy.
- (7) Brand has won numerous awards & honours.
- (8) They have a strong website www.zomato.com, which receives millions of visitors.
- (9) The mobile app has more than five million downloads globally.
- (10) The content of the mobile app is frequently updated which adds to loyal customers for repurchases.

Weakness

Zomato has the following weaknesses:

- (1) Search engine competition & rivalries apps imply restricted growth.
- (2) Rapid growth implies vulnerability to corrupt content.
- (3) Lack of training to the workforce in maintaining the standard of delivery of food.
- (4) The service in rural areas is limited.
- (5) The behavioral risk stems from online merchants that have the potential to behave opportunistically by doing fraud to the customers who place an order from distance and which are personal in nature and also the failure of the government to properly track all the online transactions. It encompasses product risks, psychological risks, and efficiency risks for sellers. The volatile existence of the Internet, which is not in the hands of the online proprietors and customers, creates environmental risk. It poses financial hazards and threats to privacy [20].
- (6) Lack of getting personal table service, inability to see physically or manage the product, and concern about processes of terms and conditions of food delivery and thereof, returns, including the dissemination of credit card number sharing over the Internet, is perceived as a drawbacks [21].
- (7) Usage of online food delivery services could minimize home cooking, which could have repercussions for customers' overall diet efficiency.

Opportunity

The opportunities in Zomato are as follows:

- (1) Opportunity to further expand to more countries.
- (2) Coverage to more semi-urban and rural areas.
- (3) Increased internet penetration with the usage of an increasing number of smartphone users.
- (4) The fast development of technology and introduction of a simpler user interface.

Challenges

Zomato has the following challenges to face:

- (1) Intense rivalry from other food aggregators.
- (2) Protecting the user data due to cyber attacks.
- (3) Lack of clear rules and regulations by the government as such business model is subject to changes due to change in government policies.
- (4) Other players can easily imitate the business model affecting the business in the long run.
- (5) In the event of disappointment, online consumers turn rapidly to rivals because options are wide without switching costs. Therefore, customer retention is a challenge for all businesses operating through the medium of online which in turn demands to put more effort and strategies for offering higher customer satisfaction [22].
- (6) Online food delivery service providers need to ensure that the food reaches the customer in a fairlead time, and the lead time should be shorter to retain the customer from taking the alternative forms [23].

X. COMPETITIVE EDGE OVER OTHER BRANDS

- (1) It utilizes several marketing tools, including SEO and SEM Comprehensively. Additionally, word-of-mouth is used which includes offline tools like publicity for out-of-home and Business-to-Business.
- (2) It also occasionally uses TV ads during High periods of activity, including Diwali, New Year, etc.
- (3) Synthetic version of its parent restaurant-finder service with huge head starts of large customer base with strong market positioning with 210 percent annual sales growth [24].
- (4) It has a user-friendly global mobile application for Operating systems for Google Android, Windows phone, IOS, and Blackberry devices. It began advertising on its mobile applications which have been fuelled by the increasing traffic on its mobile apps.
- (5) It focuses on channels of digital marketing to acquire prospective clients. It has also incorporated other instruments, such as coupons, price-offs, referrals in its marketing such as phone calls and direct mail.
- (6) Zomato's have an elevated field sales force. The ZOMANS, as the ZOMANS Members are often called, interact with company owners to sell ad space in an offline manner so that people who are not tech-savvy acquire awareness too and the customers have a wide variety to choose.
- (7) Engagement with customers plays a very important role for Zomato as such they are extremely interactive with clients through social media and apps.
- (8) It's been proven to be a large user-friendly platform for finding food spanning multiple regions and properly organized information is provided concerning restaurants, nightlife, coffee shops, luxury dining which are most popular among adolescents and foodies [25].
- (9) Zomato Gold/ Zomato Treats service is offered to customers through the Zomato App, here, clients are expected to pay a fixed fee once to obtain a membership number annually [26].

- (10) The membership scheme is also offered to the restaurants which acts as an improved promotion.
- (11) The members (customers) who opt for a free Zomato Gold get some complimentary food after the meal (including beverages) and dessert.

XI. FINDINGS

- (1) The factors that affect internet users' attitude toward online food ordering are ease of use, utility, advancement, along with trust and external influence [27].
- (2) Both large and small restaurants complain they are gradually being forced into accepting terms and conditions favourable to the aggregators. This involves financing a large part of the discounts, using only the distribution of the aggregators' fleet, a dramatic reduction in meal preparation time, and total non-transparency about how in-app recommendations operate and what restaurants should do to get recommended more often [28].
- (3) About customer details, there are few concerns to be considered; some restaurant owners say that a few major aggregators refuse to disclose information on who their customers are. In such cases, the aggregator establishes a large database of the dining preferences of customers and even grows its own business in what can be seen by restaurants as a conflict of interest [29].
- (4) There could also be challenges for individuals who are not familiar with the technology or for those who are apprehensive about the technology. These barriers would have a direct impact on the online food ordering system's satisfaction and adoption, as customers may be hesitant to place orders on the internet. People who like the expression of their opinions with personnel would also be unwilling to use the online food ordering service, which is self-serving. Restaurants should work with experts to ensure that the platform is accessible and that it performs well consistently to maintain the ordering system's consistency [30].
- (5) The experience of food operators providing quality online service was compared and the perception of the operator regarding customer taste and preferences after estimation was noted that customers use the online delivery app for convenience, speed of delivery, order, accuracy, and ease of use [31].
- (6) Product risks arise from the failure of the user to examine items online. Security threats emerge from the concern of customers that an open network on the Internet will allow their data to be compromised [32].
- (7) Usage of online food delivery services could minimize home cooking, which could have repercussions for customers' overall diet efficiency. As a result, retaining customers is difficult [33].

XII. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

- (1) In rural sectors, its reach is not very high. The brand needs to leverage it through aggressive ads, with more and more technical avenues and opening up.
- (2) Some online sites have a fake review scheme that misleads the customer. Therefore, Zomato needs to check the validity of such reviews by having a reward-based scheme.
- (3) By adding new features, such as a virtual restaurant tour, Zomato also needs to keep innovating. It must introduce live recordings and video shots from restaurants, cafes can be updated features especially if good bands are performing. To draw more consumers, the brand should use its most used features.

XIII. CONCLUSION

According to current trends, Zomato's Digital Marketing Strategy will have to keep advancing. They need to find fresh ways to draw more interest in their customers. They are doing a stellar job right now. If they continue to work hard on it, they will reap more profit. Zomato needs to be more dynamic in compete with other online food service providers by timely making changes according to customer needs.

XIV. REFERENCES

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